

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Chromosome-scale assembly of the yellow mealworm genome [version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations]

A high-quality reference genome for *Tenebrio molitor* breeding and sustainable production

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Abstract

Background: The yellow mealworm beetle, *Tenebrio molitor*, is a promising alternative protein source for animal and human nutrition and its farming involves relatively low environmental costs. For these reasons, its industrial scale production started this century. However, to optimize and breed sustainable new *T. molitor* lines, the access to its genome remains essential.

Methods: By combining Oxford Nanopore and Illumina Hi-C data, we constructed a high-quality chromosome-scale assembly of *T. molitor*. Then, we combined RNA-seq data and available coleoptera proteomes for gene prediction with GMOVE.

Results: We produced a high-quality genome with a N50 = 21.9Mb with a completeness of 99.5% and predicted 21,435 genes with a median size of 1,780 bp. Gene orthology between *T. molitor* and *Tribolium castaneum* showed a highly conserved synteny between the two coleoptera.

Conclusions: The present genome will greatly help fundamental and applied research such as genetic breeding and will contribute to the sustainable production of the yellow mealworm.

Keywords

Yellow Mealworm, *Tenebrio molitor*, genomics, chromosome-scale assembly

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Plain language summary

We provide the genome sequence of the yellow mealworm, *Tenebrio molitor*, by combining high-throughput sequencing technologies to obtain a genome assembly that well represents the 10 mealworm chromosomes. We also identified the *Tenebrio molitor* gene set and compared its organisation to that of the red beetle. This new genomic resource will help breeders to develop new mealworm lines to face future global human nutrition problems by providing protein-rich and ecologically friendly mealworm production systems.

Introduction

The global population is estimated to reach approximately nine billion people by 2050, thus the demand for animal protein is expected to increase by 76%¹. Such increase questions the sustainability of our conventional food and feed production systems. At the same time, we also need to reduce the impact of agriculture on our environment². Today, insect production is considered a sustainable alternative for food and feed production for several reasons. First, the suitable nutritional composition of edible insects³ and second, the relatively low environmental impact its production involves compared to other conventional livestock production systems^{4,5}.

In this context, the yellow mealworm beetle *Tenebrio molitor* has been described as a promising alternative protein source for animal and even human nutrition⁶. For these reasons several companies have pioneered the production of *T. molitor* at industrial scale. However, despite being promising for sustainable food security, mass production of *T. molitor* remains relatively primitive and challenging⁷.

The genetic improvement of *T. molitor* is one of these challenges. Indeed, several quantitative traits of industrial importance such as growth rate, fertility, protein rate or susceptibility to pathogens need to be mapped to allow the development of molecular-based breeding programs to speed up the development of new lines with improved agronomic traits. However, prior genomic resources on *T. molitor* are needed to accelerate such genetic programs.

Previous efforts to produce *T. molitor* transcriptomes and more recently the draft genome using 10X genomics technology have been published⁸. While this latter technology was promising on diploid and heterozygous insects^{9–12}, its application to *T. molitor* produced a fragmented assembly with a 90% of BUSCO completeness and no genome annotation. This particular effort motivated the development of a new genome assembly that would allow deeper genomic analyses such as quantitative trait locus mapping or genome estimated breeding value analysis.

Here, we propose a *T. molitor* genome assembly based on the combination of long, short reads and Hi-C data. The genome assembly and annotation quality are analysed and a comparison to the red flour beetle (*Tribolium castaneum*) genome is described to show how the current genome can be an asset for academic research and breeding.

Methods

Biological material and insect rearing

Tenebrio molitor samples were provided by Ynsect and bred at CEA-Genoscope (Evry, France). The individuals were fed with bran and apple and kept at room temperature and humidity. For the genome sequencing, male nymphs which possess XY chromosomes were selected, put on a starvation for three days and used for DNA extraction. For mRNA extraction, eggs, larva, nymphs, adult males and females were isolated without specific diet.

DNA extraction

Genomic DNA (gDNA) was extracted from a single nymph male to generate both Illumina PCR-free, PromethION and Dovetail Hi-C libraries. In order to generate long reads on the Oxford Nanopore Technologies devices, high-quality and high-molecular-weight (HMW) DNA was needed. For this purpose, DNA was isolated following the protocol provided by Oxford Nanopore Technologies, Oxford, UK (ONT), “High molecular weight gDNA extraction from plant leaves” provided by the ONT Community in March, 2019 (CTAB-Genomic-tip). This protocol involves a conventional CTAB extraction followed by purification using commercial Qiagen Genomic tips (QIAGEN, MD, USA). DNA fragment size selection was performed using Short Read Eliminator (Circulomics, MD, USA) instead of AMPpure XP beads. A single nymph male weighting 170mg was cryoground in liquid nitrogen. The fine powder was divided in one-third for Hi-C library and two-thirds for both Illumina PCR-free and PromethION libraries. The two-thirds of the powder were transferred to a lysis Carlson buffer supplemented with RNase A. After 1h-incubation, proteins were removed with chloroform centrifugation and DNA was precipitated with isopropanol and centrifugation. The pellet was then purified using the Qiagen Genomic tip 100/G, following the manufacturer's instructions. DNA was quantified by a dsDNA-specific fluorimetric quantitation method using Qubit dsDNA HS Assays (Catalog #Q32851, ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA). HMW gDNA quality was checked on a 2200 TapeStation automated electrophoresis system (Agilent, CA, USA) and the length of the DNA molecules was estimated to be over 60Kb.

PromethION library preparation and sequencing

HMW gDNA was size-selected using Short Read Eliminator kit (SKU SS-100-101-01, Circulomics, MD, USA). The ONT library was prepared according to the following protocol, using the Oxford Nanopore SQK-LSK109 kit. Genomic DNA fragments (3µg) were repaired and 3'-adenylated with the NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair Mix (Catalog#M6630, New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA) and the NEBNext® Ultra™ II End Repair/dA-Tailing Module (Catalog#E7546, NEB). Sequencing adapters provided by ONT were ligated using the NEBNext Quick Ligation Module (Catalog#E6056, NEB). After purification with AMPure XP beads (Beckmann Coulter, Brea, CA, USA), half of the library was mixed with the Sequencing Buffer (ONT) and the Loading Bead (ONT) and loaded on a PromethION R9.4.1 flow cell. The second half of the library was loaded on the flow cell after

a Nuclease Flush using the Flow Cell Wash Kit (Catalog#EXPWSH003, ONT) according to the ONT protocol. After 48h of sequencing run, a second Nuclease Flush was performed and a third library was loaded on the flow cell. Nucleotide bases were called using Guppy version 4.0.1¹³ and the raw reads were used for genome assembly.

Illumina PCR-free library preparation and sequencing

The PCR-free library was prepared using the Kapa Hyper Prep Kit (Catalog#KK8505, KapaBiosystems, Wilmington, MA, USA), following the manufacturer's recommendations. Briefly, qDNA (1.5µg) was sonicated to a 100–1,500-bp size range using a Covaris E220 sonicator (Covaris, Woburn, MA, USA). The fragments were end-repaired, then 3'-adenylated and Illumina adapters were added. The ligation products were purified with AMPure XP beads (Beckmann Coulter Genomics, Danvers, MA, USA). The library was quantified by qPCR using the KAPA Library Quantification Kit for Illumina Libraries (Catalog#07960140001, KapaBiosystems), and the library profiles were assessed on an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The libraries were sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq4000 instrument (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) using 150 bp read chemistry in paired-end mode. After the Illumina sequencing, an in-house quality control process was applied to the reads that passed the Illumina quality filters, as described by Alberti and colleagues¹⁴.

Dovetail Hi-C library preparation and sequencing

The one-third of the cryoground powder (from the DNA extraction section) was used to generate a Hi-C library using the Dovetail Hi-C preparation kit (Dovetail Genomics, Scotts Valley, CA, USA), according to the manufacturer's protocol (manual version 1.03). After the cross-linking of animal tissues, the chromatin was normalized and then immobilized on capture beads before enzyme restriction digestion. The digested DNA ends were marked with biotin and ligated to create chimeric molecules. After reversal cross-linking, DNA was purified and then followed by library generation. The Dovetail Hi-C library quality was checked as described above and sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq4000 instrument (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) using 150 base-length read chemistry in paired-end mode.

RNA extraction

Total RNA was extracted from eggs, larva, nymph and adults male and female. Tissue samples were mechanically homogenized using ZR Bashing Bead Lysis tube (ZymoResearch, CA, USA) with the FastPrep-24™ 5G Instrument (MP Biomedicals, Santa Ana, CA, USA). Nucleic acids were then extracted from homogenized suspension using the ZR-Duet DNA/RNA MiniPrep Plus kit (Catalog # D7003, ZymoResearch, CA, USA). Extracted RNA was quantified with RNA-specific fluorimetric quantitation on a Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer using Qubit RNA HS Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Integrity of total RNA was assessed on an Agilent Bioanalyzer, using the RNA 6,000 Pico LabChip kit (Catalog # 5067-1513, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA).

RNA library preparation and sequencing

RNA-seq library preparations were carried out from 500ng total RNA using the TruSeq Stranded mRNA kit (Catalog #20020595, Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA), which allows mRNA strand orientation, i.e. sequence reads occur in the same orientation as anti-sense RNA. Poly(A)+ RNA was selected with oligo(dT) beads, chemically fragmented and converted into single-stranded cDNA using random hexamer priming. Then, the second strand was generated to create double-stranded cDNA. cDNA were then 3'-adenylated, and Illumina adapters were added. Ligation products were PCR-amplified. Ready-to-sequence Illumina libraries were then quantified by qPCR using the KAPA Library Quantification Kit for Illumina Libraries (Catalog #KK4824, KapaBiosystems, Wilmington, MA, USA), and libraries profiles evaluated with an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Each library was sequenced using 151bp paired end reads chemistry on a NovaSeq 6000 Illumina sequencer.

Genome assembly

The *T. molitor* genome size was estimated using GenomeScope¹⁵ (GenomeScope, [RRID:SCR_017014](https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2019-07-01)) v1 with Illumina reads (Table S1, *Extended data*) and a *k*-mer value of 31. We applied YACRD¹⁶ (version 0.6.0) to the raw nanopore reads (Table S1, *Extended data*) to detect potential chimeras. Both “all-vs-all alignment” and “yacrd scrubbing” steps were performed with the recommended parameters and removed 109,066 chimeric reads. The 2,372,861 non-chimeric reads were corrected using NECAT¹⁷ with parameters GENOME_SIZE, PREP_OUTPUT_COVERAGE and CNS_OUTPUT_COVERAGE set to 310,000,000, 60 and 40, respectively, to first correct the longest 60x reads and afterwards, the longest 40x corrected reads were extracted to assemble 250,277 reads.

Because nanopore reads contain systematic errors in homopolymeric regions, the output assembly was polished three times using Racon¹⁸ (Racon, [RRID:SCR_017642](https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2019-07-01)) with default parameters with the nanopore reads and two times Hapo-G¹⁹ with the Illumina reads. The assembly was merged into a single haplotype genome assembly using HaploMerger2²⁰ (Figure S2, *Extended data*) and polished using two rounds of Hapo-G with the Illumina reads.

To increase the contiguity of the assembly to a chromosome-scale level (Table S1, *Extended data*), we aligned Hi-C paired-end reads to the polished haploid assembly with *bwa - mem*²¹ (BWA, [RRID:SCR_010910](https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2019-07-01)). Because Hi-C captures conformation via proximity-ligated fragments, paired-end reads are first mapped independently (as single-end reads) and subsequently paired in a later step. Hi-C reads and alignments contain experimental artifacts so the alignments need some additional processing. We use alignment filtering method using Arima Genomics pipeline (https://github.com/ArmaGenomics/mapping_pipeline) and applied the script “filter 1” to each bam file (Read1 and Read2) and afterwards paired the filtered single-end Hi-C reads using “two_read_bam_combiner.pl”. Then, with Picard tools (<https://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/>), we added read

groups to the combined BAM file (with the command AddOrReplaceReadGroups) and discarded any PCR duplicates present in the paired-end BAM file (with the command MarkDuplicates). We scaffolded the assembly with the Hi-C data using SALSA2²² and obtained 138 scaffolds. Only scaffolds larger than 35kb were kept resulting in a final assembly of 112 scaffolds (Table S3 and Figure S10, *Extended data*). The largest scaffolds were manually checked for misassembly using the sequencing information and the synteny with the ten *Tribolium castaneum* chromosomes (cf. comparative genomics section).

Transcriptome assembly

RNA-seq reads from six transcriptomes derived from different developmental stages (larvae, pupae, juveniles, adults), sexes (females and males) and public data of two RNA-seq samples generated from pooled bacterial infected *T. molitor* (PRJNA646689, *Underlying data*) were assembled using Velvet²³ (Velvet, RRID:SCR_010755) version 1.2.07 and Oases²⁴ (Oases, RRID:SCR_011896) version 0.2.08 with *k*-mer size set to 81 and 63 for the in-house and public RNA-seq reads, respectively (Table S2, *Extended data*). The contigs 5' and 3' ends were cleaned. The sequences were masked for low-complexity using DustMasker (version 1.0.0 from the BLAST 2.10.0 package) and only contigs larger than 150bp with more than 75% of unmasked bases were kept. To address the problem of merged chimeric contigs, a post-processing of Oases contigs has been done. Assembly tools often erroneously merge sequences into one single contig and Oases is prone to this behaviour. To address this problem, we used an in-house script that splits chimeric contigs. Splitting a contig into regions where different ORFs appear, or regions where abrupt shifts in read coverage occur, could streamline the gene-prediction process. Based on combined resources such as the pileup-coverage, the research of ORFs (TransDecoder <https://github.com/TransDecoder/TransDecoder/releases>) and domains, this tool aims to split contigs sequences with different functional sites from different contigs.

Genome annotation

Repeated sequence masking. Low complexity regions of the assembly were masked with the DustMasker²⁵ algorithms (version 1.0.0 from the BLAST 2.10.0 package). Transposable elements (TEs) and other repeats were annotated and masked using RepeatMasker²⁶ (RepeatMasker, RRID:SCR_012954) version open-4.0.5 with rmbblastn²⁶ version 2.10.0+. The assembly was compared to classified sequences of the RepeatMasker complete database 20150807. We set the custom library RepeatMasker.lib of version 4.0.5 to the -lib parameter²⁷.

Transcriptome and proteome alignments. mRNA contigs from the eight samples were aligned to the assembly in a two-step strategy. First, BLAT²⁸ (BLAT, RRID:SCR_011919) (version 36 with default parameters) was used for fast localizing genomic regions and the best match of each contig was kept. A second local alignment was performed with Est2Genome²⁹ (version

5.2 with default parameters). Aligned contigs with overlap higher than 80% and more than 95% identity were retained. Additionally, proteomes of four other Coleoptera (*T. castaneum*, *Ontophagus taurus*, *Asbolus verrucosus*, *Dendroctonus ponderosae*) and *T. molitor* proteins from UniProt³⁰ database were aligned to the genome in a two-step strategy. First, using BLAT (version 36 with default parameter) matches with score higher than 90% of the best match score were retained. Second, alignments were refined using Genewise³¹ (version 2.2.0 default parameters) and proteins with more than 75% of their length aligned onto the assembly were kept.

Gene predictions. To identify the gene structure, the transcriptomic and protein alignments were combined using Gmove³² (Gmove, RRID:SCR_019132) (Note S2, *Extended data*). Protein alignments from the five coleoptera were merged into a single file and provided to Gmove (-prot parameter). We also set transcriptomic alignments from eight different samples (Table S2, *Extended data*) to the -rna parameter and activated the -score option to keep the gene model with the highest score. Based on *T. castaneum* gene features, we set the maximal size of intron and minimal size of exons to 150,000bp and 3bp using the -m and -e parameters, respectively. To prevent false positive gene predictions due to a large number of single-exon transcripts, sample-specific single-exon transcripts were removed before running Gmove.

Several criteria were applied sequentially to filter the gene predictions. We used HMMER³³ (Hmmer, RRID:SCR_005305) (version 3.2.1, June 2018) to find pfam domains, DIAMOND³⁴ (DIAMOND, RRID:SCR_016071) version 0.9.24 for protein searches against ncbi-nr database, RepeatModeler³⁵ (RepeatModeler, RRID:SCR_015027) version 2.0.1 for *ab initio* repeats screening and TransposonPSI³⁶ to compare predicted models with transposable elements. Gmove initially predicted 24,870 genes, 27% of which were intronless. While we are more confident in multi-exon gene predictions we became cautious with intronless genes corresponding potentially to transposable elements or false positive predictions caused by the fragmented alignments of transcripts. To solve this problem, we launched HMMER (version 3.2.1 with e-value set to 10e-5) for detecting known pfam domains and a DIAMOND analysis against ncbi-nr database for protein hits (version 0.9.24 with -evalue 10e-5, -unal 0). Furthermore, RepeatModeler version 2.0.1 was used for screening *ab initio* repeats in the *T. molitor* assembly and 46.77% of the genome was masked. Then, we focused on overlaps between the predicted genes and repeats, using commands from BEDtools. Genes with exons highly covered by repeats (>90%) were automatically classified as repeats. In parallel, we used transposonPSI.pl to align the virtual cDNA proteins of the 24,870 predictions against the TransposonPSI_08222010 library. We selected the single best transposonPSI match for each protein (from file proteins.fasta.TPSI.topHits) and tagged the corresponding genes as transposable elements. At this point, we excluded

genes (single and multi exon) that were either highly covered by repeats (RepeatModeler) or TE tagged (TransposonPSI) without any blastp/pfam hit. We also excluded intronless genes that were predicted only by RNA-seq evidence (not any Coleoptera protein overlap) and at the same time composed of >80% untranslated regions (ratio UTR/(UTR+CDS)) without any pfam/blastp hit.

Additionally, we searched for overlaps between predicted intronless genes and CDS of proteic or mRNA evidence. Then, we discarded any intronless gene accomplishing none of the following conditions: (i) A gene that is predicted from at least one mRNA and one protein evidence. (ii) A gene that is predicted from mRNA transcripts of at least two different samples and (iii) A gene that is predicted from at least a *T. molitor* protein (from Uniprot). If none of the above criteria was met and a gene did not have any pfam/blastp hit either, then it was removed. After this filtering process the different annotation supports were combined to obtain a final set of 21,435 gene predictions (see Figure S11, *Extended data* for the genome annotation workflow).

Comparative genomics

Homology search between the 21,435 *T. molitor* predicted genes and the 22,610 *T. castaneum* protein isoforms was performed. We used blastp³⁷ (NCBI BLAST, [RRID:SCR_004870](#)) v.2.10.0+ with a maximum e-value set to 1e-10 and found 10,495 reciprocal best hits between the two species. Using NUCmer from the MUMmer4.0beta³⁸ (MUMmer, [RRID:SCR_018171](#)) package, we plotted the alignments between the 16 longest

T. molitor scaffolds and the 10 *T. castaneum* chromosomes. To observe the synteny between the two beetle genomes, we combined the associations inferred from the MUMmer plot with the localization of the orthologous genes constructed a Circos plot³⁹ (Circos, [RRID:SCR_011798](#)). Finally, 9,760 reciprocal best matches out of the total best hits (10,495) corresponded to orthologous genes between the 16 *T. molitor* scaffolds and the 10 *T. castaneum* chromosomes.

Results and discussion

Tenebrio molitor chromosome-scale genome assembly

The *T. molitor* genome size was estimated around 310 Mb with an heterozygosity rate of 1.43% (Figure S1, *Extended data*). By combining long, short reads and Hi-C data, we obtained a final genome assembly of 287.9 Mb (Table 1) representing a single haplotype of the *T. molitor* diploid genome (2n=20)⁴⁰ with a BUSCO⁴¹ (BUSCO, [RRID:SCR_015008](#)) completeness of 99.5% (using version 5.0.0 with Insecta database odb10) while the predicted genome size was 310 Mb (Figure S1, *Extended data*). The assembly presents a N50 of 21.9Mb, which is higher than *T. castaneum*'s one⁴² and much higher than the previously published *T. molitor* genome N50 (24.1kb). In our assembly, the largest 16 scaffolds represent 90% of the total assembly, leading to a chromosome-scale assembly which provides a high-quality support for gene annotation.

Nearly 6% of the assembly was masked for repeated elements with a majority of simple DNA repeats (49,992) and transposons (29,182). The next most abundant repeats were

Table 1. Assembly and BUSCO Metrics for *T. molitor* (versions 2020, 2021) and *T. castaneum*.

Assembly statistics	Tenebrio 2021	Tenebrio 2020	Tribolium
# Contigs	112 (110 nuclear + 2 mitochondrial)	31,390	2,082
Cumulative size	287,931,689	280,780,514	165,944,485
Max contig length	33,042,542	271,822	31,381,287
Mean contig length	2,570,819	8,945	79,704
N50 (L50)	21,885,684 (6)	24,131 (3,180)	15,265,516 (5)
N90 (L90)	5,674,206 (16)	3,289 (16,525)	885,624 (12)
auN	18,643,178	30,387	15,592,941
GC%	36.72%	36.03%	33.86%
Number of N	28,500 (0.01%)	0 (0.00%)	13,515,130 (8.14%)
BUSCO on genome (N = 1,367)			
Complete	1,360 (99.5%)	1,213 (88.7%)	1,357 (99.2%)
Duplicated	7 (0.5%)	52 (3.8%)	6 (0.4%)
Fragmented	3 (0.2%)	67 (4.9%)	5 (0.4%)
Missing	4 (0.3%)	87 (6.4%)	5 (0.4%)

long interspersed nuclear elements (11,417) followed by long terminal repeats (7,950). Overall, these four types of repeats account for 5.31% of the masked genome assembly (Table S4, *Extended data*).

Several studies pointed out the presence of a 142bp satellite highly present in the *T. molitor* genome^{8,43,44}. RepeatMasker detected 406 instances of the satellite repeats across 26 scaffolds covering up to 248,412 bp (or 0.08% of the assembly). Additionally, we performed a BLAST analysis with more stringent alignment parameters (BLASTn overlap >80%, identity ≥90%) and the satellite was newly detected in 17 scaffolds. We also found two variant sequences of this satellite (blastn evalue≤10e-5, word_size=10) highly represented in scaffold 23. The longest form covers approximately 89% of the satellite (126-129bp), with average identity score 77%, while the shorter one, which is more abundant, covers about 44% of satellite (62-66bp) with mean sequence similarity of 85% (Figure S5, *Extended data*).

Furthermore, mitochondrial genome was detected in two scaffolds. More precisely, the [mitochondrial genome](#) of *T. molitor* (15,785 bp) was aligned to the assembly using Minimap²⁴⁵.

It is present three times in scaffold 93 with an identity score of 85-89% (Figure S6, *Extended data*) and in several other regions of the same scaffold with a lower identity score of 53-73% (Table S5, *Extended data*). It is also found in scaffold 65 but with a lower identity score of 50-75% (Figure S7, *Extended data*). Furthermore, a 7kb region seemed common between scaffolds 65 and 94 (Figure S8, *Extended data*). This region is located at the beginning of scaffold 65 and at the end of scaffold 94 and is not covered by any Illumina mitochondrial reads (Figure S9, *Extended data*), suggesting a probable unknown part of the mitochondrial genome.

Tenebrio molitor genome annotation

By combining RNA-seq and Coleoptera proteomes, we predicted a total of 21,435 genes which is higher than the number observed in *T. castaneum*. Beside this difference, other metrics are very comparable (Table 2). Quality of the gene prediction was assessed using BUSCO version 5.0.0 with Insecta database odb10 which contains 1,367 genes and showed a gene completeness of 96.5%.

Not surprisingly, the two species share similar characteristics in terms of CDS lengths and number of exons (Figure S3,

Table 2. Annotation and BUSCO metrics for *T. molitor* 2021 and *T. castaneum*.

Annotation Statistics	Tenebrio 2021	Tribolium
Number of genes (without isoforms)	21,435	14,503
Number of intronless genes	4,898	1,109
Gene length (mean : median)	7,590 : 1,779	8,032 : 2,364
Gene length without UTR (mean : median)	5,785 : 1,147	7,900 : 2,341
Number of exons per gene (mean : median)	4.15 : 3	5.19 : 4
Number of exons per gene (mean : median) Restricted to multi-exon genes	5.08 : 4	5.54 : 4
CDSs length (mean : median)	1,177 : 783	1,839 : 1,454
CDSs length (mean : median) Restricted to multi-exon genes	1,356 : 1,071	1,921 : 1,548
Cumulative size of coding sequences (%)	25,230,147 (8.8%)	26,681,223 (16.1%)
Number of introns	67,414	60,774
Intron length (mean : median)	1,465 : 55	1,446 : 53
Percentage of contigs with >= 1 gene (% in bases)	82.9% (99.2%)	18.5% (97.6%)
BUSCO with Insecta database (N = 1,367)		
Complete	1,319 (96.5%)	1,361 (99.6%)
Duplicated	8 (0.6%)	339 (24.8%)
Fragmented	12 (0.9%)	3 (0.2%)
Missing	36 (2.6%)	3 (0.2%)

Figure 1. CDS length association for 10,495 orthologous genes of *T. molitor* and *T. castaneum*. Comparison plot with CDS lengths of *T. molitor* on x-axis and CDS lengths of *T. castaneum* on y-axis. Lengths (points) are log-scaled and coloured based on their density (highest density= yellow, lowest density=dark violet). The linear regression model best fitting the data is represented by the red-dashed line $y = a + bx$ with parameters $a=0.508$ and $b=0.939$. Higher densities are observed in the central part of the cloud and along the red-dashed fitted regression line.

Extended data) as illustrated in a linear regression model with $R^2=0.931$ (Figure 1).

After stringent gene prediction filtering (see Methods section), the gene structure patterns remained enriched in single-exon genes 22% (compared to 7% of *T. Castaneum*) (Table 2). Interestingly, 85% of them have a pfam or BlastP hit (evalue=10e-5), suggesting that they are *bona fide* gene predictions. Preliminary results show the existence of paralogous genes among them. Further investigations of gene duplication events and functional analysis have to be pursued to better understand the evolution and the biological roles of these monoexonic genes.

Macrosynteny between the *Tenebrio molitor* and *Tribolium castaneum* genomes

The macrosynteny between the *T. molitor* scaffolds and *T. castaneum* chromosomes (Figure 2) showed a strong conservation of the genome. The current *T. molitor* assembly lacks the integration of genetic data and linkage groups to reconstruct the entire chromosomes, and the assembly remains fragmented which makes the detection of possible chromosome rearrangements impossible. Future genetic works on *T. molitor* leading to the construction of a high-density map will greatly help to

anchor the current assembly on linkage groups to obtain the complete two-dimensional chromosome organisation.

Conclusions

Our sequencing and assembly strategy to build the heterozygous genome of *T. molitor* by combining long read and Hi-C showed its efficiency and provided a high-quality genome assembly and the first genome annotation with a high completeness. Thanks to this new genomic resource, future works focusing on population, quantitative and functional genomics of genes of interest will be facilitated and will greatly improve our knowledge on the molecular basis of the *T. molitor* biology. The presence of a relatively large number of monoexonic genes supported by transcripts and conserved protein domains constitutes a field of investigation to understand the biological role and the evolution of these genes. The comparison of *T. molitor* to other available Coleoptera genomes will also aid better understanding of Coleoptera evolution and diversification. Additionally, thanks to the availability of the *T. molitor* genome and genes, new breeding programs can take advantage of this resource to improve and optimize mealworm production at the industrial scale through the combination of phenotypes and whole-genome genotypes to perform genome-wide association studies,

Figure 2. Synteny between *T. molitor* and *T. castaneum*. In the right semi-circle the longest 16 *T. molitor* scaffolds are represented by orthogonal curved blocks placed next to each other. They are followed by the 10 *T. castaneum* chromosomes (left semi-circle). The unit length of the tick spacing of the blocks is 1Mb so that each block is proportional to the real size of a scaffold/chromosome. The 9,760 protein reciprocal best matches are drawn with colorful arches linking the orthologous regions between the two species.

quantitative trait locus analyses and genome estimation breeding values analysis.

Data availability

Underlying data

European Nucleotide Archive: Chromosome-scale assembly of the yellow mealworm genome. Accession number [PRJEB44684](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB44684).

European Nucleotide Archive: Chromosome-scale assembly of the yellow mealworm genome. Accession number [PRJEB44703](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB44703).

European Nucleotide Archive: Chromosome-scale assembly of the yellow mealworm genome. Accession number [PRJEB44755](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB44755).

NCBI BioProject: Mater immunity, reference transcriptome of *Tenebrio molitor*. Accession number [PRJNA646689](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA646689)

Other underlying data for the tenebrio genome are available on [GitHub](#) and [Zenodo](#).

Zenodo: madoui/Tenebrio_Genome: updated supp data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499691>⁴⁶.

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Supplementary_Data.pdf / Supplementary Table 6: Samples' accession numbers.
- Data/monoexonic (BED file with coordinates of monoexonic genes)
- Data / repeat (BED file with coordinates of the repeats)

Extended data

All extended data are available on [GitHub](#) and [Zenodo](#).

Zenodo : madoui/Tenebrio_Genome: updated supp data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499691>⁴⁶.

This project contains the following extended data within the file 'Supplementary_Data.pdf':

- Supplementary Table 1: Genomic data
- Supplementary Table 2: Transcriptomic data
- Supplementary Table 3: Metrics for long reads, contigs and scaffolds through different steps
- Supplementary Table 4: Repeats
- Supplementary Note 2: Gmove
- Supplementary Figure 1: GenomeScope Profile for *T. molitor*
- Supplementary Figure 2: K-mer plot before and after Haplomerger
- Supplementary Figure 3: Comparison of CDS lengths and number of exons of orthologous genes between *T. molitor* and *T. castaneum*
- Supplementary Figure 4: Aligning *T. molitor* to *T. castaneum*
- Supplementary Figure 5: Position of the 142 bp satellite (TMSATE1) on scaffolds 16, 58, 99, 23 and their coverage by Illumina Reads
- Supplementary Figure 6: Presence of mitochondrial genome on scaffold 94

- Supplementary Table 5: Alignment between the mitochondrial genome and the scaffold 94
- Supplementary Figure 7: Presence of mitochondrial genome on scaff 65
- Supplementary Figure 8: Alignment of scaffolds 94, 65
- Supplementary Figure 9: Coverage of scaffolds 65, 94 by Illumina mitochondrial reads
- Supplementary Figure 10: Assembly workflow
- Supplementary Figure 11: Annotation workflow

This project also contains the following extended data:

- assembly_workflow.pdf (details of the genome assembly method)
- annotation_workflow.html (details of the genome annotation method)

Data on GitHub and Zenodo are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Zero "No rights reserved" data waiver](#) (CC0 1.0 Public domain dedication).

Acknowledgements

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<http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499691>

Open Peer Review

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Barbara Feldmeyer

Senckenberg Biodiversity and Climate Research Centre, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

The authors construct a new “chromosome” assembly of the *T. molitor* genome using current state of the art technology. While the manuscript is well written and clear in most parts there are three major aspects which should be addressed before indexing of the manuscript.

General major comments

1. I find the title = chromosome scale somewhat misleading given the information later in the text. The authors obtain 112 scaffolds using the HiC data but then discuss 16 scaffolds representing 90% of the genome. Do you know/expect *T. molitor* to have 16 chromosomes? I could not find any information on that matter. Is the conclusion of having a chromosome scale assembly justified and why? Please add this information in the discussion section for example.
2. The comparative genomic section consists of a Blastp of both protein sets and a synteny plot. I understand that genome re-arrangement analyses are not feasible, but what about the gene content. Which genes or gene families are found or maybe enriched in the +5000 genes in *T. molitor*? How do repeat contents differ between species?
3. The mitochondrial sequence seems to be attached to 2 (3?) scaffolds, where it should be a single circular sequence only. This indicates some extent of misassembly and should at least be manually curated.

Introduction

- The global population: specify that you are talking about the HUMAN not beetle population.
- “However, prior genomic resources on *T. molitor* are needed to accelerate such genetic programs.”: Not sure that “prior” is the right wording here. Maybe “suitable”, or “a good quality genomes”...
- Change “Here, we propose a *T. molitor* genome assembly based” to “Here, we present”

- “kept at room temperature and humidity”: % humidity information is missing.
- Change “put on a starvation for three days” to “ were starved for three days”

Methods

- “For mRNA extraction, eggs, larva, nymphs, adult males and females were isolated without specific diet”: More information needed. Did you make one extraction from all samples, did you isolate each sample individually, did you sequence one pool or each sample individually, which kit did you use for extraction, did you Illumina sequence and which depth? => after reading further I realize that this information is given later. Maybe rephrase the sentence to “Eggs, larva, nymphs, adult males and females were collected for later mRNA extraction.”
- “HMW gDNA was size-selected using Short Read Eliminator” change to “...using the Short...”
- “following protocol, using the Oxford Nanopore” remove “using”.
- Dovetail “The one-third of the cryoground” change to “Another third of the”
- “obtained 138 scaffolds. Only scaffolds larger than 35kb were kept resulting in a final assembly of 112 scaffolds” why >35kb?
- Transcriptome “The contigs 5’ and 3’ends were cleaned.” Using which tool and parameters?
- Why did you use Velvet and Oases especially since they are prone to create chimeras? Why not use Trinity for example?
- Change “the research of ORFs” to “the identification of ORFs”.
- Change “aims to split contigs sequences” either to “aims to split contigs with different...” or “aims to split contig sequences”
- Do you make the contig splitting tool available somewhere? Is the code accessible on github or in the supplement? If so add reference.
- “BLAT (version 36 with default parameter) matches with score” change to “with a score”

Results and Discussion

- Table 1 compares the newest version of Tmolitor with the older and Tcastaneum but on contig scale. Why contig and not scaffold, or chromosome scale?
- “of 99.5% (using version 5.0.0 with Insecta database odb10) while the predicted genome size was 310 Mb (Figure S1, *Extended data*)” remove “while the predicted genome size was 310 Mb (Figure S1, *Extended data*)” from this sentence. You give this information at the beginning of the paragraph already.
- “Furthermore, mitochondrial genome” change to “ “the mitochondrial genome”.
- “More precisely, the mitochondrial genome of *T. molitor* (15,785 bp) was aligned to the

assembly using Minimap245.”: This whole mt paragraph is confusing. Do you mean you aligned an existing mt genome, from the previous assembly? From which other study? => add reference and/or accession number. And you aligned it to identify the mt genome in your assembly. Why is the mt genome split across scaffolds? It should be on single contig only? => It sounds like misassembly and should be corrected. I.e. the mt parts should be assembled into a separate mt genome and should be removed from the scaffolds.

- “a total of 21,435 genes which is higher than the number observed in *T. castaneum*”: could you discuss why you think you have more genes but lower Busco (Table2)?

Conclusions

- Change “future works” to “future work”.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Evolutionary biology, genomics, transcriptomics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Comments on this article

Version 1

Author Response 21 Feb 2022

Mohammed-Amin Madoui, 204936, France

Reviewer comments in italics.

- *I find the title = chromosome scale somewhat misleading given the information later in the text. The authors obtain 112 scaffolds using the HiC data but then discuss 16 scaffolds representing 90% of the genome. Do you know/expect T.molitor to have 16 chromosomes? I could not find any information on that matter. Is the conclusion of having a chromosome scale assembly justified and why? Please add this information in the discussion section for example.*

Response: We understand your opinion concerning the title. As *Tribolium castaneum*, *Tenebrio molitor* have 10 chromosomes (Juan, Carlos *et al.* "Improving beetle karyotype analysis: restriction endonuclease banding of *Tenebrio molitor* chromosomes." *Heredity* 65 (1990): 157-162.). We obtained one or two very large scaffolds for each chromosome (according to the synteny with *T. castaneum*) except for one chromosome corresponding to the linkage group 6 in *T. castaneum* where we obtained four large scaffolds. Thus, we used the term "chromosome-scale" because the scaffold has the chromosome length scale i.e., several megabases. We may distinguish the term "chromosome-scale" commonly used when you obtain very large scaffolds to the "telomere-to-telomere" term which is used when you obtain the complete chromosome sequences without gaps.

- *The comparative genomic section consists of a Blastp of both protein sets and a synteny plot. I understand that genome re-arrangement analyses are not feasible, but what about the gene content. Which genes or gene families are found or maybe enriched in the +5000 genes in T.molitor? How do repeat contents differ between species?*

Response: This is a very interesting point, to address this question we searched for paralogs in *T. molitor* and *T. castaneum*. We found a higher number of paralogs in *T. molitor* compared to *T. castaneum*. Among these paralogs, we found that 860 genes were histones. In the new manuscript version, we illustrated these results in Figure 1.A and Figure 1.B. The repeat analysis showed that they represent 5 to 6% of the total genome size. A detailed distribution of repeat distribution in the two genomes is now illustrated in Figure 1.C and Figure 1.D.

- *The mitochondrial sequence seems to be attached to 2 (3?) scaffolds, where it should be a single circular sequence only. This indicates some extent of misassembly and should at least be manually curated.*

Response: Indeed, the mitochondrial genome was reassembled separately and a new paragraph explains the issues we found.

- *The global population: specify that you are talking about the HUMAN not beetle population.*

Response: This is now specified.

- *"However, prior genomic resources on T. molitor are needed to accelerate such genetic programs.": Not sure that "prior" is the right wording here. Maybe "suitable", or "a good quality genomes"...*

Response: We changed "prior" by "suitable".

- *Change “Here, we propose a *T. molitor* genome assembly based” to “Here, we present”*

Response: We changed “propose” by “present”.

- *“kept at room temperature and humidity”: % humidity information is missing.*

Response: Unfortunately, the humidity was not monitored.

- *Change “put on a starvation for three days” to “were starved for three days”*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the reviewer's recommendation.

- *“For mRNA extraction, eggs, larva, nymphs, adult males and females were isolated without specific diet”: More information needed. Did you make one extraction from all samples, did you isolate each sample individually, did you sequence one pool or each sample individually, which kit did you use for extraction, did you Illumina sequence and which depth? => after reading further I realize that this information is given later. Maybe rephrase the sentence to “Eggs, larva, nymphs, adult males and females were collected for later mRNA extraction.”*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the reviewer's suggestion.

- *“HMW gDNA was size-selected using Short Read Eliminator” change to “...using the Short...”*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the reviewer's suggestion.

- *“following protocol, using the Oxford Nanopore” remove “using”.*

Response: We changed the sentence by “The ONT library was prepared with the Oxford Nanopore SQK-LSK109 kit, according to the following protocol”.

- *Dovetail “The one-third of the cryoground” change to “Another third of the”*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the reviewer's suggestion.

- *“obtained 138 scaffolds. Only scaffolds larger than 35kb were kept resulting in a final assembly of 112 scaffolds” why >35kb?*

Response: It corresponds to the size of the shortest Nanopore read supported by the NECAT assembler.

- *Transcriptome “The contigs 5' and 3'ends were cleaned.” Using which tool and parameters?*

Response: We did not use a specific tool to clean the contigs. Now, we precise the way the contigs are cleaned as follow “The first five bases of the contigs 5' and 3' ends containing N's were removed”

- *Why did you use Velvet and Oases especially since they are prone to create chimeras? Why not use*

Trinity for example?

Response: Trinity was tested, it produced the shortest contigs and the gene prediction using the Trinity contigs had a lower BUSCO score.

- *Change “the research of ORFs” to “the identification of ORFs”.*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the reviewer’s suggestion

- *Change “aims to split contigs sequences” either to “aims to split contigs with different...” or “aims to split contig sequences”*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the second reviewer’s suggestion.

- *Do you make the contig splitting tool available somewhere? Is the code accessible on github or in the supplement? If so, add reference.*

Response: To perform this task, we used a custom in-house perl script that is not portable on other platforms. However, for reproducibility of our results, we provide the details of the method: Reads were mapped to the contigs with BWA-mem (Li *et al.*, 2009) and the consistent paired-end reads were selected. Chimeric contigs were identified and split (uncovered regions) based on coverage information from consistent paired-end reads. Moreover, open reading frames (ORF) and domains were searched using respectively TransDecoder (Haas *et al.*, 2013) and CDDsearch (Marchler-Bauer *et al.*, 2011). We only allowed breaks outside ORF and domains. Finally, the read strand information was used to correctly orient the RNA-seq contigs. This method is now clearly explained as part of the Materials and Methods section.

- *“BLAT (version 36 with default parameter) matches with score” change to “with a score”*

Response: We changed the sentence according to the second reviewer’s suggestion Results and Discussion.

- *Table 1 compares the newest version of Tmolitor with the older and Tcastaneum but on contig scale. Why contig and not scaffold, or chromosome scale?*

Response: We compared the scaffolds in both cases, we replaced the word “contig” by “scaffold” in table 1.

- *“of 99.5% (using version 5.0.0 with Insecta database odb10) while the predicted genome size was 310 Mb (Figure S1, Extended data)” remove “while the predicted genome size was 310 Mb (Figure S1, Extended data)” from this sentence. You give this information at the beginning of the paragraph already.*

Response: This element has been removed

- *“Furthermore, mitochondrial genome” change to “the mitochondrial genome”.*

Response: This has been changed.

- *“More precisely, the mitochondrial genome of *T. molitor* (15,785 bp) was aligned to the assembly using Minimap245.”: This whole mt paragraph is confusing. Do you mean you aligned an existing mt genome, from the previous assembly? From which other study? => add reference and/or accession number. And you aligned it to identify the mt genome in your assembly. Why is the mt genome split across scaffolds? It should be on single contig only? => It sounds like misassembly and should be corrected. I.e. the mt parts should be assembled into a separate mt genome and should be removed from the scaffolds.*

Response: We aligned this mitochondrial genome <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucore/KF418153> to our assembly (in the original article, “mitochondrial genome” is a link leading to the ncbi page). The mitochondrial genome is found in scaffold_94 three times. In general, mitochondrial genomes are more covered by reads than other regions. So, the assembler may have estimated multiple copy. As for scaffold_65, it is not a completely mitochondrial sequence. It looks more like an insertion of the mitochondrial genome has occurred in the nuclear genome which is commonly observed. Thus, the scaffold_65 was kept in the genome assembly. The misassembly on scaffold 94 could be resolved by choosing one single copy (the one in the middle of the scaffold having the best match-length and identity percentage to the mitochondrial genome of NCBI). However, in that way, we would not be able to assemble it with the part of 7kb. So, we prefer to simply remove this scaffold from the assembly.

- *“a total of 21,435 genes which is higher than the number observed in *T. castaneum*”: could you discuss why you think you have more genes but lower Busco (Table2)?*

Response: Indeed, we observe more genes but a lower busco score in *T. molitor*. By analysing the missing busco genes in *Tenebrio*, we found that they were found in *Tribolium* isoforms. As we do not propose isoforms in the gene prediction, it is possible that we oversee these genes.

- *Change “future works” to “future work”.*

Response: This has been modified

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
